

**DIALECTIC COMPLEX WORDS
WITH SUBORDINATE RELATIONS
IN UZBEK DIALECTS OF THE
REPUBLIC KARAKALPAKSTAN**

Linguistics

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Abstract

The given article is devoted to the scantily explored problems of derivitology of Uzbek language – the analysis of forming complex dialecticism with subordinating relationship of components in Uzbek dialects of Karakalpakstan. On the basis of analysis the number of linguistic materials is distinguished the productive ties and fictive ways of forming complex dialectal words: noun+noun; noun=adjective; number+noun and etc.

In dialectic word combinations with affixal derivation is taken great place as compound word in Uzbek. (5:2007, 5-6). There is widely shown compound words in Uzbek dialects of the Karakalpak language, components which are found between itself in subordinated attitude. However, nature of the registration of components of such addition doesn't present uniformity. So, interrelations of components of compound words *dabsandiq* (Khodj., Kipch., Nazx.): *ullarzha* (Sarab., Shorkh., Elk., Guld.): *nahan archa* (Kung., Shum., Kanlk.) "big trunk" is attributive, that is the first component acts as definition of the second component, while interrelations between components of compound words *yechki emer* "shape of lizard" (Khodj., Mang., Kipch., Bibz., Bern.); *yeshakemi* (Mang., Bern., Bibz., Kilchb.): *ehsakemi* (Turk., Elk., Sarab.) - "allergic illness" complete, object, as first component acts as a role of second's object. Such compound words in Turkic is accepted to name the adding an attributive and complete relations of components (1:1982, 20,21,82). Each of these types with subordinated relative components in UzSk has several types and models. However, all of them in lexico-grammatical and semantically relations are the comprehensive whole in dialectic semantics.

There are some specific characters for the complex dialect words:

1. There is no dialectic formation in the list of all complex dialect words, each of the component which is used in the language literature, not forming complex words: *kurpayorindja* "third rising of lyustern" (Turk., Sarab., Elk.), *Umirzaya* "Star of Venus" (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Shumn.), *iytkuylak* "the first dress for the new born baby" (Kung., Kanlk., Shumn., Khodj.);

2. The same lexical units in literary language form different compound dialect words: Ex: *ak* "white" forms: *akbaskin* "underground" (Kung., Kanlk., Shumn.), *akbikech* "millet" (Kung.), *akbilak* "beauty", *dilavar* "speaker", "improvizator" (Khodj., Kipch., Kung.), *karasan* "the illness of horned cattle" (Kung., Takrk., Nazkh.), *akmarka* "brem" (Kung., Kanlk., Shumn., Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh., Takrk., Bibz., Bern.);

3. In the process of forming dialect words take part either literary words, or dialect words:

a) the first component- literary word, the second – dialectic word. *temirjaba* “pitchfork” (Khodj., Kung., Kipch.) compare “jaba“ (the device to pull out hay from stach), *marazchop* “weed” (Khodj., Kung.), *koljap* “small stream” (Khodj.), *kamirturish* “yeast” (Kung., Shumn., Kanli., Kipch., Mang.);

b) the first component –dialectic word, the second- literary word: *godjakarin* (Khodj., Kung.), *pulkanan* “loaf” (Khodj. Nuk.), *kompaynan* (Kung., Shumn., Kanlk.), *sansan postin* “fur coat” (Khodj. Kipch., Mang.);

4. There are some borrowing in the structure of the dialectic words:

a) the first component –borrowing word: *shirchay* “tea with milk” (Mang., Bibz., Bern., Naym.) from persian “shir” (milk). *Lampamay* “kerosin” (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Kipch., Bibz., Bern., Nazkh.) from persian “neft” (2:1965,113). *Pishtaban* “low hee led boots” (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Shumn.), *yakhsuv* “winter watering” from persian “yakh” (cold) (Khodj., Bibz. Sarb.);

b) the second component- borrowed word: *ashkadi* “pumpkin” (Turtk., Elk., Sarb.) from persian “kadu”;

c) compound words, consist of jus borrowed words: *paytaba* “foot wrap” (Beru., Bibz., Kipch.) from Persian “pay” (foot), “tab” (basis) past from verb *tabidan* and *tofdan* “rolling” (2:1965,113), *apbashare* “view”, “face” (Khodj., Bibz., Bern.) from persian *aft+fishan* “face+look, appearance”, *gavgum* “the time of twilight” tadj. Govgum (gov –cow, gum- wanted - (2:1965,113)- the time when its difficult to find the cow in the darkness, disappeared cow), *payapul//ayak kupir* “bridge for walking” (Mang. (2:1965.113), Khodj., Bibz., Bern., Sarb.) –from tadj. “pa”, “pay” (foot), “pul” (bridge), *atashkir* “fire irons for takin off coal” (Khodj., Kipch., Beru.)-from Persian “atash” (fire) “*gur, gir*” (taking, holding). (2:1965.113),

5. There are some words in the list of compound dialectic words which historically met different changes (shortening affixes, base changes form and some phonetic changes, etc.)

a) as the result of changing forms it was appeared variants of compound dialectic words: *paystun* “wooden pedestal” (Turtk., Elk., Benr.), *takyamat* “felt” (Khodj., Kipch., Bern., Bibz.) – from persian “tag” (down), “namat” (**koshma**);

b) as the result of changing structure of complex words component in literary style: lit. *tishkankuyrik* –dial. “tishkankuyrik” type of local carrot (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk., Shumn., Nuk., Kipch.) “mouse’s burrow”, *karatuyak* is the illness of the horned cattle, (Khodj., Kipch., Kung., Kanlk., Nazkh.), *tabanan* bread baked in the pan. It’s clear that, all Turkic scientists differ ideas about classification and investigation of compound words. We held the opinion suggested by F.Ganieva (1:1982,31).

Dialective compound words in Uzbek mark out from dialective compound nouns, which are unproductive:

“Noun+Noun”: *daragach* “wood for drying clothes” (Khodj., Bibz., Bern.), *khinachop* “knout stick”, *kariysorak* (Kung., Kanlk., Shumn., Khodj.), *toptayak* “kids game” (Kung., Kanlk., Khodj., Nazkh.), *khirmantup* “left seed” (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk.);

“Noun+Derivative noun”: *bashsalma* “head channel” (Bibz., Beru.), *nantuvrama* “type of meal”, *temirsuvlik* “bit” (Khodj., Kipch., Beru.);

“Noun+Adjective” *kakkurt* “diary dried product” (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk.), *kagerik* “dried apricot”, *kharamchop* “weed” (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk.), *yavoyot* (Turt., Elk., Beru., Bibz.), *kizilmagiz* “sort of watermelon” (Beru., Mang., Kalk.), *karapochaq* “illness of watermelon”, *lakkitabak* “small day cap” (Bibz., Beru., Sarb.), *karakatti* “sort of watermelon” (Khodj., Kipch., Kung.);

“Derivative adjective+noun”: *ziyanlizhandik* “predators” (Khodj., Shumn., Kalk., Kung.), *kallikol* (Kanlk., Kipch., Kung.);

“Numeral+Noun”: *uchchayrak* “private domain of one person” (Kipch., Mang., Nazkh., Khodj.), *ucham kozi* “triplet lambs” (Ter., Sir), *yikkavat: yikkat* “pregnant”, *segizkoz* “bach” (Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh., Mang., Bibz.), *beshbarmak* “sort of meal” (Khodj., Kung., Kalk., Nuk.);

“Numeral+participle”: *birkirkar* “the last born lamb” (Chap.), *birtuvgan* “pure-bred camel”, *tishyargan, tishburgan: dish buzan* “two year cow”;

“Verb+Noun”: *buktize* “equipment for preparing horse” (Kung.), *utrokmok* “cudgel” (Naym), *esersok* “mad, crazy” (Khodj., Nuk., Kanlk., Kung.);

There are some unproductive words:

“Adverb+Adverb”: *dustomen* “down” (Kung., Kanlk., Khodj.), *naganda* “seldom” (Kung., Kanlk., Nuk.), *yenevel* “first of all” “at the beginning” (Mang., Bibz., Beru.), *atamzaman* “very long ago” (Kung., Kanlk., Nuk., Khodj.), *almisak* (Mang., Bibz., Beru., Sarb.);

“Numeral+Adverb”: *birzamatta, birmaydanda* “in a blink” (Beru., Sarb.), *yekibashtan* “certain” (Kipch., Khodj., Bibz., Beru.), *yekyesaptan* “surely, certainly” (Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh.);

“Noun+Noun”: *zhildin zhili* “yearly, annual”, *ayagusti* “in a hurry” (Khodj., Mang., Bibz., Beru.).

There are some other unproductive sorts of dialective adverbs: *muzday aman* “successfully” (Uzun.), *muz karakesek* “very cold” (Khodj., Kipch., Mang.), *khadden tish* “beyond one’s strength” (Nazkh., Kipch., Khit.), *khadden ziyat* (Khodj., Nuk., Bibz., Beru., Mang.).

Dialectic compound words with other other parts of speech are also unproductive. So, the words formed with pronouns: *iechkayda* “nowhere” (Khodj., Kipch.), *ichkim* “no one”, *issat* “nothing” (Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh.), *nezat* “what is it”, *iechkim* “no one”, *kimmurtti* “kids game” (Khodj., Kipch., Bibz.), with modal word *djok-urijoq* “no will”, *kamiyok* “decent”.

As the first component of dialectic compound words with attributive features can be almost all parts of the speech, which are differ with their productiveness. In lexics the first components of compound words are related to different categories. They can be illustrated an examples of dialectic compound nouns, and the first component denotes followings:

1. Form of object represented by the second component: *atjal* “defect” (Khodj., Nazkh., Bibz.) word for word translation “horse+mane”, “narrow line of grass which was left at mowing, and looks like mane horse”, *ayudjilan* “big poisonous snake” (Kanlk., Kung., Shumn., Khodj.) word for word “bear+snake”; *ataviz* “pliers fire iron” (Khodj., Kipch., Mang., Beru.) word for word “mouth of horse”;

2. Material of object represented by the second component: *mistaba* “tea-tray” (Beru., Bibz., Nazkh., Khodj.) word for word “copper+pan”, “the pan is made of copper”. Compare *tashtabak* “the cap is made of clay” (Khodj., Kung., Kipch., Mang., Beru.), *chalikora* “cattle-shed” “pen is built of cane or twig” (Khodj., Kipch., Nazkh., Kung., Kalk.);

3. Usage of the object: *djaynamaz* “rug for praying” (Turt., Beru., Nazkh., Khodj.), *ayakkap* “shoes” (Kung., Kanlk., Shumn., Khodj.), *kirkalta* “kit-bag for dirty clothes” (Kung.), *inyagash* “yoke” (Khodj., Kipch., Kung.), *ashtakta* “board for rolling out tough”;

4. Quality, features of object is represented by the second component: *kakchakka* “thin, sick” (Khodj., Kipch., Bibz., Beru.), *chudjemurin* (Khodj., Nuk.);

5. State, position of the object is represented by the second component: *kishamkozi* “lamb of the last cattle” (Beru., Bibz., Mang., Khodj.), *zhugirme kachar* “heifer” (Takrk.), *akabasuv* “much water” (Khodj., Kipch., Kung., Mang.), *karamai* “resin” (Khodj., Nazkh., Kipch., Kung.);

6. Location, origin of object is represented by the second component: *shirgurich* “boiled rise with milk” (Turk., Sarb.), *nayman juvari* “sort of seed” (Khodj., Mang., Kilch.), *bukhari bash* “sort of wheat”;

7. Time of the object is represented by the second component: *kun tun* “whole day”, *tanierten* “tomorrow” (Turk.), *tanmal* “early morning” (Kung., Nazkh., Nuk.), *taltush* “afternoon” (Khodj., Kipch.), *chankaytush* (Kung., Kanlk., Nuk., Takrk.);

8. Appearance of the object is represented by the second component: *burgiballik* “small fish” (Khodj.), *donizot* “brown color of weed” (Khodj., Kipch., Kung., Kanlk.), *djelkesuv* “water of main channel” (Kung., Kanlk. Khodj.);

9. The result of acting is represented by the second component: *tashkalil* “strong guaranteeing”, *alopki* “cattle’s pneumonia”, *pakhtamay* “vegetable oil” (Beru., Khodj., Bibz.), *akmay* (Nuk., Shumn., Kanlk., Kung.), *donmay:tonmay* “tat”, *sutemgan* “six month lamb or calf” (Khodj., Kung., Kanlk.);

10. Possession of the object is represented by the second component: *kogerish suvi* “the first watering process for cotton fields” (Mang., Beru.), *torgay oti* “plant which grows on sal- cellar” (Khodj., Nazkh.), *chit mayi* “cotton oil” (Turt., Beru., Elk.);

11. Size and number of the object are represented by the second component: *bir kulak suv* “little size water” (Tarb.), *kilakasa* “litre size cup” (Kipch., Khodj., Nazkh.), *bir kitak djer* “one fourth of domain” (Djuv.);

12. Colour of the object is represented : *alabaris* “clay area”, *akbaypak* “illness of the cattle” (Kilch.), *akkuv* “swan”, *bozturgay* “bird”, *akbash* “plant”, *karakash* “ethnonim” (Khodj., Nuk.), *kara tirishmay* “cholera”, *kogegish* “vegetable manufacture”;

To the list of this kind of compound words we may include complex verbs and nouns, which have objective and modifier between components.

In the structure of compound verbs, differ from other parts speech, first component there is usually noun and adjective, as the second component there is auxiliary verb. Auxiliary verbs are productive in combination with proper words *bol* –“to be”, *sal* –“to put”, “lay down”, *kil* –“do”, *et*- “to do”, less productives are *al* –“take”, “get”, *chik*-“to go out”, unproductive are *koy*-“put”, “lay down”, *yasa*-“to do”, “to make”, “to create”, *kel* -“to come in”, “to visit”, *bar*-“to go”, “to send”, *ach*-“to open”, *yur*-“to go”, *kal* -“to stay”, *tush*-“to fall”, “to go down” etc. F.A. Ganieva called them functional auxiliary verbs, taking into consideration that they are verbs and just in the process of derivating compound structure. They are the function of auxiliary verb (1:1982.88).

“Noun+Verb “*bol*” in the meaning “to act”, “to do”, which represented by the first component: *puchbol* “dry up”, “wilt”;

“Noun + Verb “*sal*” in the meaning “to cut” represented by the first component” *at sal* “to carry on secret negotiations”, *bas sal* “imediately”, “to wager”;

“Noun + Verb “*kil*” in the meaning “to do” something which represents first component: *ziyan kil* “to harm”, *abay kil* “threaten”, *tonkarish kil:avdarish kil* “to do revolution”

“Noun + Verb “*et*” to act something or process which represented by the first component: *davush et* “to bewail”, *khaz et* “to be happy”, *mink etmiydi* “to keep silent”, *epu et* “to sorry”.

So dialective compound words with subordinating components are widely depicted in Uzb, they are differing with lexical-semantic structure and correlation of components. We investigated productive sorts of compound nouns, with attributives and compound verbs with complex correlation of components, less productive sorts are adjectives and adverbs.

It was identified homonymic and synonymic correlation between compound words, which have dialectic features.

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Abbreviations:

Beru. – Beruniy region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Bibz. – village Bibiazar in Beruniy region.

Kanlk. – Kanlikol region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Kung. - Kungrad region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Sarb. – Sarabiy village in Ellikkala region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Turt. – Turtkul region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Mang. – Amudarya region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Khodj. – Khodjeyli region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Elk. – Ellikkala region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.